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Exploring the Marist Traits Exemplified by School Administrators: An Autoethnographic Study

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Abstract

This study was made to unveil and describe the Marist traits exemplified by school administrators in the performance of their function in the school setting. As an autoethnographic study, it used self-introspection with the help of guide questions to elicit information such as personal traits of school administrators and whether such traits were aligned to Marist teachings. The introspective focus made by the participant-researchers (school administrators) through guide questions provided the results that school administrators had their own characteristics or values in the performance of their task. Furthermore, data revealed that such qualities as exemplified by the administrators were found to be not different from Marist teachings as they unknowingly exemplified such personal traits in the performance of their role in the school setting.

Keywords: *Marist traits, school administrators, autoethnographic study*

Introduction

This study has been made and inspired by the life of St. Marcellin Champagnat whose religious vocation and traits became pedagogical examples for present generations of Christian faithful and for students who studied in Marist schools.

For centuries now Marist teaching and philosophy spread all over the world mainly through educational institutions established by Marist Brothers with Saint Marcellin Champagnat as the founder. Love for children and the care for the less advantage are some of the qualities that this religious group have imparted and shared worldwide. Mohamad (2016) said that Marist teaching such as hard work and excellence were valued, genuine love for others and strong family spirit, and simplicity must be evident in the lives of Marist Brothers. The life of Saint Marcellin Champagnat taught humanity how beautiful it is to live a life with values and character and be exemplified as we journey to our own path of life. Love for people particularly to the young minds is one distinct characteristic of Marist brothers that needs to resonate in order to help the young people to grow and be matured.

Today, it is evident that many schools are practicing Marist values and teachings. This only means that Marist teachings are useful as guiding principles in the school setting. In fact, these distinct Marist principles like humility, prudence and love are found visible among graduates of Marist school institutions. Some of these graduates are now school administrators with Marist values lingering in their hearts and minds. These administrators claimed that Marist teachings contributed a lot to them personally and during the times when they are confronted with problems and challenges. They said that Marist teachings helped them to decide well during difficult situations. Green (2021) states that one of the Marist teaching states that the glory of God would be evident in the ways that clarity, creativity, equity of opportunity, principled action, and justice-with-mercy are being learned and practiced by most of the people.

While many educators and school administrators have exhibited, knowingly or unknowingly, Marist teachings, there is still a need to reconfirm through repeated studies whether Marist pedagogy continues to propel educational institutions and the people towards greater heights. It was on this basis that this study was made to explore and describe the traits and values possessed by school administrators and how these traits have been exemplified in accordance to the Marist teachings and principles like humility, prudence, gentleness, patience, and love.

Research Objective

This study aims to describe how Marist traits and teachings exemplified by the participant as the researchers on their journey as school administrators.

Methodology

This study purely conceptualize by the researchers as the participants. The participant-researchers used an autoethnographic qualitative research design which used guide questions for self-introspection in order to elicit the values exemplified by school administrators in the performance of their function and responsibility in the school setting. This was conducted by two students who took Educ 361 Seminar Workshop on Marist Pedagogy at Notre Dame of Marbel University, who were themselves the participants of the research. The participant-researchers incidentally both handled administrative functions in their school.

The first participant-researcher is connected at Department of Education as District Supervisor of Maitum 1 District at the same time the School Principal of Malalag Central Elementary School-SPED Center. The second participant-researcher was a University CWTS Program Head and Emergency and COVID-19 Incident Commander. Aside from the testimonies made by the participant-researchers, the contents posted and shared in the Schoology and the inputs made during the class sessions were also used as sources to support the narrative made by the researchers.

Data Gathering Tools and Data Analysis Techniques

The researcher-participants met together at NDMU. The one-on-one interview was made alternately using the guide questions, directing the participants to engage in self-introspection. The first participant-researcher threw all questions first and recorded the answers to the questions. The second participant-researcher did the same to the first participant.

The study employed Generic Qualitative Data Analysis Technique which used Yin’s thematic analysis in order to come up with common themes based on the narrative shared by the participants.

Table 1. Yin’s Thematic Analysis

Guide Questions	Self-Introspection Responses	Key Concepts	Themes
What administrative position do you handle in school?	Currently, I am a District Supervisor of Maitum 1 District and concurrent school principal of Malalag Central Elementary School-SPED Center	A District Supervisor and School Principal	
What personal values do you practice as an administrator?	I am designated with S.O. as NSTP-CWTS Head Program Coordinator and the University Emergency and COVID-19 Incident Commander As a school leader the personal values I am practicing are being; Dedicated to my work sinisigurado ko na natatapos ko ang aking trabaho before deadlines and I need to perform well for my professional and personal growth. Committed, in the sense that I need to commit myself to my work because I strongly believe that this is my source of living and my happiness as well and, Motivated, in the sense that I need to impart to myself that I need focus and motivation for me to accomplish things with feeling of satisfaction. I am loyal and committed to the institution and its principles I work sincerely for the good of the group or the institution and I prefer that everyone would take part in the decision-making process especially if the work requires major support from my colleagues	Designated as the NSTP-CWTS Head Program Coordinator and the University Emergency and COVID-19 Incident Commander Dedication and commitment to one’s job in finding happiness Loyalty and commitment to one’s organization and its principles	Professionalism, Commitment and Efficiency
What Marist traits do administrator should possess?	The Marist traits that need to be possessed as school administrator are, 1. Humility, being humble and simple all the time which love from others is manifested in your daily task. 2. Gentleness, being gentle to your people and being calm all the time. 3. Patience, patience is virtue and this is one that a leader must possess because all of our request are in place and be given to you in God’s perfect time. 4. Prudence, that our judgment is valued with respect and with integrity especially during decision making. 5. Love, love to our work and to the people around us.	Consistency in being humble through simplicity in actions, and letting others see your love through daily work Maintaining calm and kind demeanor all the time Patience as a virtue that ensures answers from God in perfect timing Making judgments with respect and integrity particularly during decision-making process Demonstrate love not only to work but to people you deal with	Consistency in Humility
Among Marist traits, which do you consider the most significant to imbibe by an administrator?	For me as a leader, the five (5) Marist values are needed to be imbibed by an administrator because they are necessary and vital in dealing with our colleagues as well in doing our task. The Marist Pedagogy taught us how to become a good leader with humility, gentleness, with patience and prudence. As for me, humility is the most significant Marist trait. Humility is the fountain of grace and wisdom. Jesus Christ even denies the “divine” which many ordinary people cannot give up. When we are at the	Values like humility, gentleness, patience, prudence, and love are crucial for working with colleagues and fulfilling our tasks Humility as the source of grace and wisdom. We overlook the preciousness of ordinary things in life when we aim for greatness	Leadership values, i.e. the Marist virtues, are important in working with colleagues and accomplishing tasks effectively

‘height’ it is hard to see ordinary things. We wanted more big things, great things that we fail to see that the most ordinary in life is the most precious one.

Among the Marist traits, what do you possess as school administrator?

As I evaluated myself after taking up Marist Pedagogy the traits that I possess are
1. Humility, I am just a low profile school leader in our District I am dealing with my colleagues with a humble heart because I strongly believe that I can make decisions if I put myself to the level of my subordinates and I need to feel what are their clamor and suggestions as well.
2. Gentleness. I make sure that in my daily routine I need to calm myself despite of many challenges, I need to be gentle to my colleagues for them not fell awkward every time I am dealing with them.

Maintaining awareness of one’s position as a low-profile school leader in the district emphasizes the importance of dealing colleagues with a humble heart and helps in effective decision making as they understand the perspectives of subordinates by actively listening to their suggestions

Effective Leadership in Education

In what ways did you employ Marist traits you possess in dealing school concerns?

Prudence. As an administrator one needs to be tactful and be very careful in words and language to say. It is part of prudence to consider the people you lead as human beings with full of potentialities and undiscovered talents.

Maintaining calm disposition amidst challenges creates comfortable feeling to colleagues during interactions

Dealing with the teachers is a major part of my daily task such as how to improve their teaching and learning styles, tasking them with different works and dealing with their diverse attitudes and outlooks in life.

An administrator has to be careful in choosing words and languages Working closely with teachers to enhance their teaching methods and overall learning experiences

Educational Leadership and Well-being

During decision making, there were times that I was being challenged by the situation. Maintaining in mind the Marist teaching, everytime I make decisions, I tried to be prudent and calm. These are the values that I think that need to impart.

Making decisions guided by Marist teaching like prudence and wisdom during difficult situations

In dealing with my personal concerns, sometimes I feel burn out and being challenged with many task to perform, a lot of things to be done and being patient and gentle to the situation is necessary for our health purposes.

When managing my personal issues, I sometimes experience burnout due to numerous tasks and responsibilities. It's essential for our well-being to remain patient and calm during such challenging times

I had to act prudently in giving back NSTP-CWTS loads to the college which offered the degree program. It was stressful and a real headache considering that the office does not have regular faculty to handle the CWTS class. The higher ups were convinced to monetize the loads or convert to service credits the unit loads. We were left unburdened by this arrangement.

Lacking permanent instructors to handle the course led to negotiation which was tedious and burdensome

Results and Discussion

In exploring the Marist traits exemplified by the school administrators it is

reflected the seven themes that occur during the discussions of the participant-researchers. It was described as the fundamental principles and how the Marist traits must be exemplified into the life of the school administrators.

Professionalism

It is common that these concepts are important in both personal and professional life. For most people the word professional has been taken ordinarily as having earned a college degree. For some people, a professional is a person who gets paid by his skill and service rendered in a professional setting. All these are not enough to say that a person is professional. For one may be able to carry out his job very well but failed to exemplify basic qualities how it is to be truly a professional in the truest sense of the word.

The participant-researcher emphasize that a true professional is one who adheres to the highest standard of morality. The hallmarks of a person with the highest sense of morality are honesty and trustworthiness in his or her interactions with other people. Truly, when one devotes his time selflessly in order to efficiently carry out his work is an example of honesty and trustworthiness. One cannot be said to exemplify professionalism if he does not have the commitment to finish on time the work at hand and finish them effectively and efficiently for the good of the organization. They adheres that professionalism entails carrying out one's work with quality. And this professionalism is not only felt and seen with high-quality results of work but always in concomitant with ethical behavior from the person.

Commitment

The participant-researchers discussed commitment as working more than personal satisfaction but working for the greater good of the people in an organization. Commitment is more felt by the impact an administrator has made to his or her subordinates. The participants agreed the principle of Abdullah (2021) that commitment is understood as the employees' constructive emotional bonding to the organization. The more love we put to our work the more we become humble and committed to it. Like many Marist had said the more they work in school, the more they turn to be humble. Indeed, the growth of an organization largely depends upon the commitment of the leaders of an organization, driving the subordinates to perform better after realizing the sincerity of the leader or administrator in carrying out the goals of the organization.

Efficiency

This must something to work on as school administrator. It entails courage and motivation towards work as we played the vital role. The participants experienced being efficient in his working place as it is expected to perform due to the demand and the standards occurred. They say that being efficient must something to exemplify by the school administrator for them to beat the deadlines and perform their duty in admirable way. Being efficient leader is already an innate values that must be perform because many of the colleagues depend on the actions and decisions on different situation.

In addition, the participants states that being efficient is superb in handling school resources, manage its fund base on the plans which is implemented with quality, has a big impact to school improvement and it must be implemented base on the timelines set by the planning team.

Consistency in Humility

The hardest yet the best pedagogical example ever taught to us by Jesus Christ is humility. God the Father humbles himself in the person of Jesus Christ. Christ lived a humble life. He was ostracized and got no support from the people around him. St. Marcellin Champagnat also experienced the same. He did not receive immediate support of his religious aspirations and advocacy from the people surrounding him. Yet, St. Marcellin remained humble, simple in his actions, and continued his advocacy to help the simple people, the poor people.

The participants describe that the key to effective and efficient administration of an institution is for the leaders to live the virtue of humility and simplicity. Humility truly brings positive atmosphere in running an institution. Such gesture of administrators brings out the potential of the members of an organization, leading towards harmonious relationship between and among members of the group. Simplicity in our actions just like Jesus Christ truly will lead us to a meaningful life. Harmonious relationship is not only measured by the number of people we have as friends but by the quality of the interactions and impact we have made with these people. And harmonious relationship always starts from within through our constant communication with God. It is indeed a manifestation of humility when we recognize from within our inadequacy and we start to relate to a Being whom we recognize as above and beyond us, who is God the Most High.

Leadership Values (the Marist virtues) are Important in Working with Colleagues and Accomplishing Tasks Effectively

In olden days, the main determinant of success in one's career and happy life was pure intelligence. Geniuses in the past were known to be secured and assured of good life as they had a good chance of landing a promising job. Overtime, this outlook has changed. Many intelligent people in the past have turned their lives into a mess simply because they did not have good attitude or behavior. High intelligence in no way guarantees success and true happiness in life.

The true indicators of success and happiness in one's career and both in personal and community life are the values like humility, patience, gentleness, prudence, and selfless love. For many people the great motivators of their lives are fame, honor, prestige, and wealth. These people function very well as individuals because of the influence of these worldly possessions. Lest they understand that the greatest source of inspiration comes from things that are unseen. Real authority comes not from physical things but from things which are not seen by our naked eyes.

Marist traits are values that have helped administrators developed good leadership. Great things have been achieved and accomplished by the great leaders in history not by virtue of the intelligence, influence and wealth they own but by the values they uphold in the performance of their role as leaders. Indeed, the traits that brought great leader towards greater success are the same virtues taught by St. Champagnat which have been exemplified also by the school administrators like humility, prudence, gentleness, and love.

Effective Leadership in Education

All of us can lead but not all leaders can lead effectively. Undeniably, the foundational qualities of Marist contributed to effective leadership by those who have had embraced them. Those who imbibed Marist principles became passionate in what they do and developed the ability to lead people of diverse culture. The participants describe that effective leadership can be measured depending on what aspect we consider a leader would be evaluated. An education leader can be said to be effective if he is able to transform the physical aspects of his or her school from having old buildings and infrastructure to modern infrastructure and establishment. Or, effective leadership in education can be said to be real when the institution is able to receive awards and recognition for its outstanding accomplishment in instruction, research and human resource development. High results of board exams, number of takers who passed the entrance test, increase in the number of employees' promotion may count as indicators of effective leadership. While they may count as physical indicators, they may not necessarily indicate as the 'real' indicators of success. These things may come as façade only and in essence not the measure of effective leadership.

Upon close consideration, the researcher- participants emphasized that measure of effective leadership would always point to the traits and values that leaders have exemplified in the performance of their function as a leader. Gentleness in dealing with subordinates, listening to the subordinates' comments and suggestions, calm dispositions in dealing in all matters that pertain to work life and personal life of the subordinates, the choice of words, language and manner of speech are an overarching values and traits which will ensure effective leadership in education. All these traits are the fundamental teachings of Marist education. The physical endowments and material possessions may have an effect but are short-lived. The participants emphasize that the essence and life-giving principles that make effective leadership in education are the ideals which the Marist teaching advocated for so long a time such as humility, gentleness, prudence and love.

Educational Leadership and Well-being

"No pain, no gain" as the saying goes. There are a lot of sacrifices to be made if one is to become a leader. Certainly, a person with leadership must have had experiences of difficulty with fellow workers in the work setting. In the context of educational institutions, leadership can be more challenging. Imagine how much of one's self be given considering the many people in the organization with different backgrounds and orientations. It would be difficult to bring them into one decision if and when there is an issue at hand. It will drain so much of an energy of a leader if his or her total well-being is not prepared to undertake such challenge. Even if we just provide guidance to these people, it will take so much of the leader to do so.

The researcher-participants says that even how much pain a leader would suffer in the performance of his role, if the leader remains virtuous, he would survive them all whatever it takes. Truly, the secret of happiness and success are the possession of long-held values like humility, gentleness, prudence, and love. These Marist principles are proven to have provided more life to the career of school administrators. A good leader has to remain full of love, calm and patient in all of his or her actions.

Conclusions

As educators and administrators, we have embraced the core values of Marist principles, as exemplified by St. Marcellin Champagnat, and have humbly integrated these virtues into our educational roles. We recognize that our actions as administrators align with universal values such as professionalism and commitment, with love being the most crucial Marist principle, particularly in the complex environment of educational institutions. Humility serves as the foundation that enables us to express our love and dedication in our work. By sincerely striving for the best interests of our subordinates, we foster a sense of care and concern among them. When Marist principles like humility, prudence, gentleness, and love become second nature, they facilitate harmonious relationships and effective performance in the workplace, with love overcoming barriers and strengthening connections with our colleagues.

References

- Elvery, J. (2013). *Understanding and implementing the Marist Charism from the Middle: The Experience of Middle Leaders in a Marist School*, Australia Catholic University, Australia
- Green, M. (2021). *Marist Education: Creative fidelity to its sources*, Australia
- Sammon, S (1999). *A heart that knew no bounds, Saint Marcellin Champagnat: The life and Mission*. Istituto dei Fratelli Maristi, Roma Italia

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